

SHORT NOTES

Mucilage from the Fruits *Bhendi*

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The fruits of *Abelmoschus esculentus* are known as *Bhendi* and used as vegetables. The crushed fruits yield a thick viscous solution in water from which a mucilage is obtained by precipitation with ethanol as a grey fibrous mass. A preliminary examination of the mucilage gave positive tests for protein and carbohydrates. It has ash, 11.0; N, 3.26; acetyl, 2.5 and methoxyl, 0.7%. Attempts to remove the inorganic material by precipitation with acidic ethanol from the solution failed. The ash dissolved in HCl (dil.) and showed presence of Fe^{3+} , Ca^{+} , and PO_4^{3-} .

Chromatography of the hydrolysate of the mucilage by 8 *N*-HCl showed presence of the following amino-acids. These were estimated using standard methods and characterized by isolation and formation of suitable derivatives wherever possible. The presence of an amino-sugar was also detected.

TABLE I

Amino-acid.	% Dry mucilage.
1. Histidine	1.1
2. Arginine	0.6
3. Lysine	4.7
4. Glutamic acid	0.8
5. Serine	7.2
6. Alanine	0.6
Total	15.0

Chromatographic examination of the hydrolysate by 1*N*-HCl indicated the presence of glucose and glucosamine, which could be isolated as its hydrochloride; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 70.5^\circ$ (*c*, 4 in water). Estimation of glucosamine¹ showed 10.1% of this sugar in the mucilage. Glucose was the only sugar in the hydrolysate.

Hydrolysis of the mucilage by 0.5*N*-Ba(OH)₂ yielded a tetrasaccharide composed of *D*-glucose and glucosamine in the proportion of 3:1. The tetrasaccharide showed $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 97.1^\circ$ (*c*, 2 in water); N, 2.1%; M.W., 650, (cryoscopic).

The above results are in sharp contrast to those obtained by Whistler and Conard² and Amin³ on the mucilage from Okra fruits (*Hibiscus esculentus*). The above authors

1. Elson and Morgan, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, 20, 1824.
2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1673, 3374.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 928.

found the mucilage to consist of D-galactose, D-galacturonic acid and D-rhamnose. None of the above sugars were found in the mucilage described in this communication.

Isolation.—Fruits, free from seeds, were minced in a Waring blender and kept in contact with water overnight. The viscous solution was pressed through a piece of muslin and added to ethanol (4 volumes). The mucilage, which separated as a sticky mass, gave a grey powder on trituration with ethanol (yield, 0.6; ash, 11.9; N, 3.26; acetyl, 2.5; methoxyl, 0.7% on dry basis). The mucilage dissolved in water to form a viscous solution. The ash content could not be reduced by precipitation with EtOH-HCl.

Hydrolysis.—The mucilage (10.0 g.) was hydrolysed with 8*N*-HCl at 90° for 24 hrs. The hydrolysate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. Paper chromatography showed the presence of glutamic acid, arginine, histidine, lysine, serine, and alanine. These results were confirmed by running authentic specimens side by side. Histidine was isolated as the nitroanilate, arginine as flavianate (m.p. 258°), and lysine as picrate (m.p. 261°). Glutamic acid was isolated using the method of Jones and Moeller⁴ and converted to the hydrochloride, m.p. 210°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 31.7^\circ$ (*c*, 4 in 20% HCl). The filtrates on removal of the above acids were used for the estimation of serine⁵. Alanine was weighed as such.

Identification of Sugars.—Hydrolysis of the mucilage (10.0 g.) with 2*N*-HCl (500 ml) for 24 hrs. at 90° gave, on removal of HCl with silver carbonate, sugars as a syrup. Paper chromatography indicated presence of only two sugars, viz., glucose and glucosamine. Glucosamine was isolated as the hydrochloride; $[\alpha]_D^{25} 70.5^\circ$ (*c*, 4 in water). Glucose was identified in the filtrate of the hydrochloride by preparing osazone, m.p. 203°.

Isolation of a Tetrasaccharide.—The mucilage (20 g.) was heated with 0.5*N*-Ba(OH)₂ (500 ml) on a water bath for 10 hrs. The suspension was cooled and filtered. The precipitate was washed with hot water (2 × 100 ml). Ba²⁺ was removed by addition of H₂SO₄ in requisite amount. Barium sulphate was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to 50 ml under reduced pressure. The concentrate gave a yellow powder on precipitation with ethanol. It was purified by dissolving in water and treating with Norit. The sugar was obtained as a white powder, m.p. 60-65°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 97.1^\circ$ (*c*, 2 in water); N, 2.1%. On hydrolysis with 1*N*-HCl for 10 hrs. at 90°, it showed presence of glucose and glucosamine. The latter constituted 24% of the total sugar. Molecular weight (cryoscopic) was 650. A tetrasaccharide composed of 3 molecules of glucose and 1 molecule of glucosamine requires glucosamine 26.9; N, 2.1%; M.W., 665.

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4. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 79, 429.

5. Boyd and Logan, *ibid.*, 1942, 146, 279.